

Probabilistic Risk-Aware Flight Trajectory Planning under Convective Weather

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Abstract—Effective management of severe weather impact on air traffic management system and flight operations is important for improving the safety and cost-efficiency of aircraft operations. In this paper, we present the Risk-Aware Weather Rapidly Exploring Random Trees Star (RAW-RRT^{*}) algorithm that incorporates online weather risk assessment into flight trajectory planning at a tactical stage.

Unlike traditional deterministic methods that reroute flights around weather-affected area boundaries based on a single forecast, our approach treats the weather forecasting problem as an image-to-image translation problem, using U-Net based architectures along with the Monte Carlo Dropout, to predict the future weather intensity, its uncertainty, and changes in location and shape with calibrated radar data in a probabilistic manner.

We quantify the overall risk of a flight trajectory as the joint probability that the entire path is exposed to hazardous weather, and we use this risk measure as a constraint, along with the flight separation requirements and aircraft dynamics, into a heuristic that also accounts for both fuel consumption and flight distance. Given the nature of atmospheric dynamics, the weather intensities and uncertainties are correlated across both space and time, the feasibility of a flight path cannot be assessed by assuming independence between different time steps or locations. Thus, the online weather risk assessment in our trajectory planning method considers not only the intensity and spatial boundaries of a convective weather, but also the spatiotemporal variations within and between individual weather cells by calculating the covariance between them along the flight trajectory.

By means of a user-defined trajectory-wise weather risk threshold, we evaluate our approach through simulation experiments under three different traffic densities, and the results show that our proposed RAW-RRT^{*} method is capable of generating conflict-free and efficient trajectories while maintaining safety within the threshold.

Keywords—probabilistic thunderstorm avoidance; risk assessment; aircraft trajectory planning

I. INTRODUCTION

Adverse weather phenomena significantly disrupt air traffic management (ATM), often leading to substantial delays. In the event of convective weather, the available airspace volume reduces as air traffic controllers reroute flights to avoid

weather hazards, creating unusual and complex traffic patterns. In these scenarios, both pilots and air traffic controllers experience an increased workload for several reasons. Air-crew typically have more accurate and up-to-date information on convective weather due to their onboard radar—often more reliable than data available to air traffic control (ATC), which can sometimes be limited or nonexistent. As a result, pilots frequently request deviations from their planned routes to avoid hazardous weather. ATC then has to handle these deviation requests while also assess surrounding air traffic to maintain safe separation and decide whether to grant the clearances. In turn, this process leads to more frequent radio communications, the emergence irregular traffic patterns, and unexpected crossing points, complicating conflict detection and resolution for ATC and potentially requiring more coordination between ATC sectors as well [1]. These factors translate into a reduction of the airspace capacity, may prompt air traffic flow management regulations, such as regulated take-off times, and in extreme scenarios might compromise safety. Under these circumstances, a decision support tool capable of automatically generating flight trajectories for convective weather avoidance could help reduce workload for both pilots and controllers, thus mitigating capacity reduction and maintaining safe and efficient operations.

A key challenge in dealing with convective weather arises from the inherent difficulty in predicting the exact initiation and evolution of these phenomena. Traditionally, flight trajectory planning in weather avoidance models, such as the en-route convective weather avoidance model (CWAM) [2], are calculated by routing around adverse weather represented as polygon areas. These areas are defined using deterministic forecasts that transform radar echo top height and vertically integrated liquid data into fields for weather avoidance. The edges of predicted weather are used to cluster pixels, which are then enclosed in convex hulls based on a predefined threshold. Such deterministic approaches rely on a single forecast scenario without quantifying the uncertainties involved, which often leads to conservative and less robust flight planning as the flights are rerouted around the entire

weather-affected region, rather than considering potentially feasible paths through areas with lower risk.

A recent trend is to capture the inherent uncertainties of weather forecasts. In the pure nowcasting field, [3] combines physical-evolution schemes and conditional-learning methods to address the inherent difficulty of nowcasting, which stems from multiscale and multiphysics problems arising in the atmosphere. From a trajectory planning perspective, one of the attempts is to deduce spatial uncertainty out of a set of nowcast data by quantifying the nowcast uncertainty as a margin to enhance flight trajectory planning in case of adverse weather [4]. The determination of spatial nowcast uncertainty is based on the statistical analysis of the maximum deviation between predicted and observed weather fields. Nevertheless, using an arbitrary spatial uncertainty margin could result in excessively large areas that are designated as no-go zones, leading to inefficient routing.

Other trajectory planning methods integrate the uncertain motion of convective weather into deterministic nowcasting systems. For example, [5] models the probability of a location falling within a convective storm based on its evolution, formulating the problem as a robust optimal control trajectory planning task that balances flight time and weather exposure. However, this method does not account for changes in storm intensity or shape, representing the detected storms as rectangular regions with proportional margins instead. A more advanced work done by [6] uses model predictive control to avoid moving and size-changing ellipsoidal storms in a deterministic framework. In [7], weather scenarios are generated using the Ensemble Prediction System forecasts, assuming that each ensemble member occurs with equal probability. At each position, a random number is drawn from a uniform distribution. If the drawn number is lower than the storm probability at that location, a storm is assigned. Similar to [2], the storm-affected positions in [7] are clustered and convex polygons are generated to enclose each cluster. This process is repeated across multiple times to account for weather uncertainty. The safety of a trajectory is evaluated based on its intersection with these hazardous regions from each ensemble member, treating them as deterministic.

In aforementioned methods, although uncertainty in the location and boundary of weather-affected regions is considered, the regions themselves along with the safety constraints are treated deterministically, without evaluating the variations in weather intensity within them or potential risk of flying through them. Consequently, a fixed probability bound is applied uniformly across all boundaries, regardless how likely they are to cause infeasibility, leading to overly conservative trajectory planning [8].

In contrast to existing probabilistic weather avoidance methods—where risk is simply calculated as the likelihood that a given trajectory point falls within a storm cell without considering how earlier trajectory decisions influence later risk or how weather cells interact [7, 9, 10]—this paper introduces a cumulative, trajectory-wide risk measure. This measure incorporates the spatiotemporal correlations between

weather cells and accounts for the impact of previous trajectory decisions. As a result it offers a more realistic and efficient way to evaluate overall weather risk in flight trajectory planning during flight execution phase. We summarize the main contribution of this paper as follows.

- 1) Probabilistic weather forecasting. With recent advances in computer vision and the increased availability of radar image data, our method uses U-Net architectures to model and predict future radar reflectivity (i.e., weather intensity). We treat the network as an approximate Bayesian model, so that the uncertainty in each weather cell's intensity across space and time is estimated.
- 2) Trajectory-wise risk assessment. We introduce the overall risk of a flight trajectory as the joint probability that the entire path encounters hazardous weather. Given the nature of atmospheric dynamics, the uncertainty is correlated, and thus we cannot assume independence between time steps when checking the feasibility of a flight path. Instead, we incorporate not only the predicted weather intensity and the spatial extent of the convective weather, but also the spatiotemporal relationships among weather cells by calculating their covariance along the flight path.
- 3) Risk-Aware Weather Rapidly Exploring Random Trees Star (RAW-RRT*) multi-flight trajectory planning. We integrate the probabilistic risk measure with a heuristic that accounts for fuel consumption and flight distance. Our approach considers the scenarios in which the aircraft has already departed but has not yet entered the region of interest. In this setting, we plan the trajectory to balance maintaining weather risk within a user-defined threshold and optimizing overall flight performance during the flight execution phase.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Traditional trajectory planning in weather avoidance relies on deterministic methods that specify weather boundaries without quantifying trajectory-wise risk introduced by the flown path, variations in weather intensity or the uncertainty in those forecasts. In such methods, the outcome of any action on trajectory sequence is assumed to be known beforehand, so operational factors such as flight trajectory updates or the availability of environment state information do not affect the optimization formulation and corresponding risk calculation. In our problem, adverse weather is not only dynamic but also uncertain in its intensity, location, and shape. Moreover, weather cells encountered along a flight path interact with each other, affecting the overall risk. This inherent uncertainty requires a probabilistic approach that quantifies the trajectory-wise risk arising from variable weather conditions and associated spatiotemporal uncertainties. An overview of our framework is as shown in Fig. 1.

In this study, we focus on flight execution operations for the en-route flights, rather than potential air traffic flow

Figure 1: Concept diagram of the proposed risk-aware trajectory planning framework in uncertain weather environments. Historical radar observations feed into the weather prediction module. By training multiple models, we obtain probabilistic predictions of radar reflectivity along with estimates of uncertainty. These forecasts are then used in the online risk assessment that evaluates the likelihood of encountering hazardous weather along a planned trajectory, accounting for the spatiotemporal correlations among weather cells. At the same time, the tactical trajectory planner considers aircraft dynamics constraints and separation requirement to avoid conflicts with other flights.

management measures that could have been applied before departure.

We define an area of interest within the airspace where severe weather conditions necessitate avoidance. To support this, the following assumptions are made in this paper:

- 1) aircraft intersecting this region has to replan its trajectory to avoid severe weather cells;
- 2) this trajectory replanning is handled centrally to ensure weather avoidance trajectories remain conflict-free; and
- 3) avoidance trajectories do not need to follow published en-route procedures (i.e., airways), mimicking, to some extent, current operations where ATC grants avoidance headings (i.e., vectors) upon the requests made by the aircraft crew.

Consequently, the outcome of our approach is a new risk-aware trajectory for each aircraft, accommodating adverse weather avoidance, while respecting separation requirements with other aircraft in the same area.

In order to plan a trajectory under such uncertainty, we need to predict the future distribution of adverse weather and evaluate the feasibility of an entire flight path. Let us define the aircraft trajectory as $\Gamma = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_K\}$ where K is the total number of discrete steps along the trajectory, and s_k is the aircraft state vector at step k . Given an initial state and a goal state, our objective is to find an optimal trajectory that

achieves the following:

- 1) Minimization of a cost function. In this study, we consider both fuel consumption and flight distance.
- 2) Satisfaction of feasibility constraints. This includes following aircraft dynamics, maintaining separation requirements between aircraft, and ensuring that the overall weather risk remains within a threshold.

Adverse weather is modeled as dynamic obstacle whose positions, intensities, and boundaries are uncertain. Moreover, the temporal and spatial dependencies between weather cells affect the overall risk experienced along a flight path. Therefore, the challenge in our study is to formulate an optimization problem that incorporates the trajectory-wise probabilistic risk of encountering hazardous weather while balancing operational efficiency.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Aircraft Dynamics

In this paper, the aircraft is represented using a point-mass model with variable velocity at a constant altitude, considering only en-route flight. We assume that lateral avoidance is preferred over vertical avoidance due to possible severe turbulence, wind shear, microbursts, and hail at different altitudes.

The aircraft performance model is based on the BADA v3.x model [11]. We then assume that the velocity remains steady between two consecutive trajectory planning points, and any changes in the aircraft's speed occur instantaneously. In this paper the effect of wind is also neglected from the dynamic equations.

Taking above considerations into account, the motion of the aircraft is described by the following differential equations:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ \lambda \\ m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{v \cos(\chi)}{R_E + h} \\ \frac{v \sin(\chi)}{(R_E + h) \cos \phi} \\ -f_{cr}(T) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where ϕ is the latitude, λ is the longitude, v is the true airspeed (TAS) with wind neglected, m is the aircraft mass, and χ is the true heading angle. The altitude is denoted as h , and R_E represents the mean radius of the Earth. T is the thrust force, and fuel flow f_c is modeled as a function of thrust. The drag force D is expressed as:

$$D = \frac{1}{2} \rho S_w v^2 C_D, \quad (2)$$

where C_D is the drag coefficient, ρ is the air density, and S_w is the reference wing surface area.

In BADA family 3 model, the thrust specific fuel consumption η is specified as a function of the TAS as follows [12]:

$$\eta = C_{f1} \left(1 + \frac{v}{C_{f2}} \right), \quad (3)$$

where C_{f1} and C_{f2} are fuel flow coefficients for different aircraft types that are specified by the BADA model. Then, the cruise fuel flow f_{cr} is calculated using η and a cruise fuel flow factor C_{fcr} :

$$f_{cr} = \eta T C_{fcr}. \quad (4)$$

We can then describe the dynamics of the aircraft using the state vector $\mathbf{s} = [\phi, \lambda, m]^\top$, and the control vector $\mathbf{u} = [\chi, v]^\top$. If we discretise these vectors, the aircraft trajectory can be modeled as the evolution of the state vector \mathbf{s}_k under the control vector \mathbf{u}_k over time as follows:

$$\mathbf{s}_{k+1} = \mathbf{s}_k + \Delta t \cdot \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{u}_k), \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{f} is the vector function representing the dynamic system of Eq. (1).

B. Flight Separation Requirement

We simplify the separation provision between each pair of aircraft considering only horizontal separation. Hence, the horizontal distance between any given pair of aircraft is expressed as:

$$d(\mathbf{s}^q, \mathbf{s}^l) \geq d_{\min}, \quad (6)$$

where $d(\cdot)$ is the great-circle distance between two aircraft states $\mathbf{s}^q, \mathbf{s}^l$ corresponding to aircraft q and l . In this paper, we set d_{\min} to 5 nautical miles, which is the minimum horizontal separation in standard radar controlled en-route environments.

To maintain the separation requirement effectively, we implement a ‘‘First Come, First Serve’’ strategy for simplicity, though our framework can accommodate other prioritization policies. Under this strategy, aircraft are prioritized by the order in which they enter the region of interest, allowing higher-priority aircraft maintain their planned trajectories as much as possible, while lower-priority aircraft adjust their paths when necessary. The trajectories of all higher-priority can be treated as dynamic obstacles that must be avoid, where the avoiding strategy is detailed in the following section.

C. Probabilistic Convective Weather Risk Modeling

In this section, we aim at learning the 2-D horizontal movement and evolution of spatiotemporal weather fields from radar image data, modeling the inherent uncertainty, to provide probabilistic radar reflectivity prediction for modeling the future probability distribution of weather risk.

Given a sequence of radar images over time, $\mathbf{X}_{1:T} = \{\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2, \dots, \mathbf{X}_T\}$, $\mathbf{X}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$, $\forall t$ where H and W are the spatial dimensions of the input radar image. We employ the U-Net [13] and RainNet [14] architecture to predict a series of weather field image \mathbf{X}_{T+1} and beyond, through a convolutional neural network. We further extend these architectures to estimate the mean and variance for each radar pixel grid by training independent models.

The weather field prediction model follows an encoder-decoder architecture in which the encoder progressively reduces the spatial resolution through pooling and convolutional layers to extract high-level features, while the decoder progressively restores the spatial resolution using upsampling and convolutional layers, reconstructing the weather field image with temporal and spatial patterns. For training, we use the log-cosh loss function, defined as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^W \ln(\cosh(\hat{x}_{ij} - x_{ij})), \quad (7)$$

where \hat{x}_{ij} and x_{ij} represent the predicted and observed precipitation values at the pixel grid (i, j) . The structure of the network is detailed in [14].

A straightforward approach to estimate the variance of the weather field image prediction is to train a model with dropout and evaluate N times via Monte Carlo Dropout [15], treating the network as an approximate Bayesian model. In each iteration at the evaluation stage, the model is considered as a distinct sample drawn from its posterior distribution, and each output from these iterations represents a distinct sample from the predictive distribution, denoted as \hat{x}_{ij}^n for the

n^{th} evaluating iteration, parameterized by randomly masked weights $\hat{\omega}_n$ according to a Dropout distribution [16].

The empirical mean for pixel grid (i, j) at time t is then the mean of the predictions from all N iterations:

$$\mu_{\hat{x}_{ij}}(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{x}_{ij}^{\omega_n}(t). \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the empirical variance for same pixel can be estimated as the sample variance of the individual model predictions:

$$\sigma_{\hat{x}_{ij}}^2(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\hat{x}_{ij}^{\omega_n}(t) - \mu_{\hat{x}_{ij}}(t) \right)^2. \quad (9)$$

The resulting probabilistic model for the continuous value at pixel (i, j) and time t can therefore be expressed as a time-dependent normal distribution:

$$\hat{x}_{ij}(t) \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\mu_{\hat{x}_{ij}}(t), \sigma_{\hat{x}_{ij}}^2(t) \right). \quad (10)$$

The radar reflectivity vector along the trajectory Γ , denoted as \mathbf{x} , is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}_1(t_1) \\ \hat{x}_2(t_2) \\ \vdots \\ \hat{x}_K(t_K) \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}}), \quad (11)$$

where $\hat{x}_k(t_k) = \hat{x}_{i_k j_k}(t_k)$ is the predicted precipitation value at radar pixel (i_k, j_k) corresponding to state vector \mathbf{s}_k ¹ and time t_k . $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\mathbf{x}}$ is the mean vector of the multivariate normal distribution, and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{x}}$ is the covariance matrix that accounts for the dependencies between the weather intensities at different trajectory points at different time.

Following guidance from FAA Advisory Circulars [18], weather radar echo intensities are measured in dBZ on radar images. Using this, we denote a radar reflectivity ξ and an user-defined maximum allowable probability of violating the constraint ϵ .

Since we want to limit the probability of the aircraft encountering a hazardous weather situation that persists or extends over a significant portion of the planned trajectory, we define the total weather risk of the trajectory R_{Γ} as a joint probability. R_{Γ} calculates the likelihood that the entire trajectory lies in hazardous regions where the radar reflectivity exceeds the threshold ξ , it is given by:

$$R_{\Gamma} = \mathbb{P} \left(\bigcap_{k=1}^K \{ \hat{x}_k(t_k) \geq \xi \} \right) \leq \epsilon. \quad (12)$$

However, directly computing R_{Γ} is too computationally expensive because it involves a correlated multivariate normal distribution, where the weather events are likely both spatial

¹The spatial reference for each radar pixel grid is a polar-stereographic projected Cartesian coordinate system [17].

and temporal dependent. The key step is to calculate the joint probability incrementally based on trajectory progress. Using the chain rule of probability, we can decompose the joint distribution into a product of conditional probabilities, so that Eq.(12) is reformulated as:

$$R_{\Gamma} = \prod_{k=1}^K \mathbb{P} \left(\hat{x}_k(t_k) \geq \xi \mid \hat{x}_1(t_1), \dots, \hat{x}_{k-1}(t_{k-1}) \right). \quad (13)$$

D. Risk-Aware Trajectory Optimization

The primary objective of our trajectory planning problem is to reach the goal point in minimum time and fuel burn while ensuring that the probability of the planned trajectory exceeding the user-defined weather risk threshold remains below an allowable probability along the entire trajectory. We define the optimization problem as:

$$\arg \min_{\mathbf{s}} (\omega_m(m_o - m_d) + \omega_d d_{\Gamma}), \quad (14)$$

where $(m_o - m_d)$ is the fuel burn between origin and destination, d_{Γ} is the total distance of flight, and ω_m, ω_d represent the non-dimensional weights of fuel burn and distance of flight, respectively.

To check the feasibility along the trajectory for each aircraft, we extend the chance constraints Rapidly Exploring Random Trees (CC-RRT) algorithm [19] with online risk assessment as RAW-RRT* for our conflict-free path planning problem.

Let a tree be represented as $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{E})$, where each node $a_k \in \mathcal{A}$ corresponds to a state vector \mathbf{s}_k ; and each edge $e_k \in \mathcal{E}$ represents the transition from \mathbf{s}_k to \mathbf{s}_{k+1} , as defined in Eq.(5). The RAW-RRT* algorithm evaluates the feasibility of each node using Eq.(13) while expanding the tree and add nodes only when they are found feasible.

For a new node trying to be added into the tree \mathcal{G} , the covariance matrix $\Sigma_{1:k}$ that represents the uncertainties and dependencies among the existing path expands to $\Sigma_{1:k+1}$. Properties of the Schur complement [20] are used in updating the inverse covariance matrix $\Sigma_{1:q+1}^{-1}$, based on the existing inverse covariance matrix $\Sigma_{1:k}^{-1}$, without recomputing the entire matrix from scratch. Let \mathbf{c} be the covariance vector that follows the spatiotemporal exponential decay model between the new node and all existing nodes. Using the Schur complement we have:

$$\Sigma_{1:k+1}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} + \frac{\Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c}^{\top} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1}}{\sigma_{k+1,k+1} - \mathbf{c}^{\top} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} \mathbf{c}} & -\frac{\Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} \mathbf{c}}{\sigma_{k+1,k+1} - \mathbf{c}^{\top} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} \mathbf{c}} \\ -\frac{\mathbf{c}^{\top} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1}}{\sigma_{k+1,k+1} - \mathbf{c}^{\top} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} \mathbf{c}} & \frac{1}{\sigma_{k+1,k+1} - \mathbf{c}^{\top} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} \mathbf{c}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

The conditional mean and conditional variance are given as:

$$\mu_{k+1|1:k} = \mu_{k+1} + \mathbf{c}^{\top} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_{1:k} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{1:k}), \quad (16a)$$

$$\sigma_{k+1|1:k}^2 = \sigma_{k+1,k+1} - \mathbf{c}^{\top} \Sigma_{1:k}^{-1} \mathbf{c}. \quad (16b)$$

We can now calculate the conditional probability that the new node's radar echo intensity exceeds the threshold ξ :

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\hat{x}_{k+1} \geq \xi \mid \mathbf{x}_{1:k} \right) = 1 - \Phi \left(\frac{\xi - \mu_{k+1|1:k}}{\sigma_{k+1|1:k}} \right), \quad (17)$$

and the total risk for the updated trajectory $\Gamma_{1:k+1}$ can then be expressed as:

$$R_{\Gamma_{1:k+1}} = R_{\Gamma_{1:k}} \times \mathbb{P}(\hat{x}_{k+1} \geq \xi \mid \mathbf{x}_{1:k}) \leq \epsilon. \quad (18)$$

The main structure and logic of the RAW-RRT* search technique is given in Algorithm 1, which iteratively grows a tree for each aircraft A_c .

Different aircraft are processed based on the order given by a priority list \mathcal{I} . For each aircraft, we define its start and destination nodes denote as a_o and a_d . When the Algorithm 1 is called for a selected aircraft, it initially adds a_o to its tree \mathcal{G}_c . Several functions for RAW-RRT* are explained as follows:

- 1) **Rand** : Sample a random node a_{rand} from the aircraft state vector space \mathcal{S} , subject to the aircraft dynamic constraints.
- 2) **Nearest** : Identify $a_{\text{nearest}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ based on the Euclidean distance.
- 3) **Steer** : Generate a new node a_{new} by moving from a_{nearest} towards a_{rand} , respecting the aircraft dynamics equations (1), with step size Δt , minimizing the cost function Eq.(14).
- 4) **FeasibilityCheck** : Check whether the path between two nodes satisfies the minimum separation requirements and the risk threshold given in Eq.(6) and Eq.(18).
- 5) **NearK** : Identify a set of nodes $\mathcal{A}_{\text{near}} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ based on k-nearest search.

Algorithm 1: RAW-RRT* Main Procedure

```

1  $\mathcal{A} \leftarrow \{a_o\}$ ;  $\mathcal{E} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2 for iter = 1 to MaxIter do
3    $a_{\text{rand}} \leftarrow \text{Rand}()$ 
4    $a_{\text{nearest}} \leftarrow \text{Nearest}(a_{\text{rand}})$ 
5    $a_{\text{new}} \leftarrow \text{Steer}(a_{\text{nearest}}, a_{\text{rand}})$ 
6   if FeasibilityCheck( $a_{\text{nearest}}, a_{\text{new}}$ ) then
7      $\mathcal{A} \leftarrow \mathcal{A} \cup \{a_{\text{new}}\}$ 
8      $\mathcal{A}_{\text{near}} \leftarrow \text{NearK}(a_{\text{new}})$ 
9      $a_{\text{min}} \leftarrow a_{\text{nearest}}$ 
10     $c_{\text{min}} \leftarrow \text{Cost}(a_{\text{nearest}}) + \text{Cost}(a_{\text{nearest}}, a_{\text{new}})$ 
11    for  $a_n \in \mathcal{A}_{\text{near}}$  do
12       $c_{\text{temp}} \leftarrow \text{Cost}(a_n) + \text{Cost}(a_n, a_{\text{new}})$ 
13      if FeasibilityCheck( $a_n, a_{\text{new}}$ ) and
14        ( $c_{\text{temp}} < c_{\text{min}}$ ) then
15         $a_{\text{min}} \leftarrow a_n$ 
16         $c_{\text{min}} \leftarrow c_{\text{temp}}$ 
17     $\mathcal{E} \leftarrow \mathcal{E} \cup \{(a_{\text{min}}, a_{\text{new}})\}$ 
18 return ( $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{E}$ )

```

IV. EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

In this section, the proposed RAW-RRT* algorithm is tested over a one-hour period using the dynamic aircraft

model detailed in Section III-A, at a constant flight level FL310 within the area of interest defined as $\mathcal{X} = \{(\phi, \lambda) \mid 47.5^\circ\text{N} \leq \phi \leq 50^\circ\text{N}, 8^\circ\text{E} \leq \lambda \leq 14^\circ\text{E}\}$. The heading between any two consecutive nodes $\{a_k, a_{k+1}\} \in \mathcal{A}$ are assumed to be constant.

We use the publicly available radar data with quality-checked (RY) product provided by German Weather Service (Deutscher Wetterdienst DWD, Offenbach) [21]. This dataset covers an area of 900 km by 900 km over Germany, with a resolution of 1 km and updates every five minutes. Within region \mathcal{X} , we detect summer weather events from this dataset on May 29, 2016, between 18:00 to 20:00 UTC.

To align with FAA Advisory Circulars [18], we use the refined radar reflectivity to rain rate (Z-R) relationship table described in [22] to calculate radar reflectivity from the original dataset, i.e., the calibrated precipitation depth data. An example of the converted radar reflectivity data used in probabilistic weather prediction modeling within the defined area is shown in Fig 2.

Figure 2: Radar reflectivity observation at 29th May 2016, 18:40 UTC.

A. Scenario and Parameter Setup

1) *Simulation Environment*: To simulate flight trajectory replanning at tactical level, we set a 20-minute time horizon as the lead time. Four consecutive radar composite grids, recorded at 18:40, 18:45, 18:50, and 18:55 on May 29, 2016, are used as input channels to generate a nowcast for 19:00 UTC. To extend the prediction period from 19:00 to 20:00 UTC, a recursive approach is implemented by using the model's predictions at 5-minute lead times as inputs for subsequent forecasts, thereby achieving continuous prediction over the entire one-hour window.

To predict the adverse weather and quantify its uncertainty, we start with a pre-trained deterministic model based on [14]. We then process the aforementioned radar image data through 30 iterative evaluations, each time applying dropout to the network's layers. After these evaluations, we calculate the mean and standard deviation of the outputs to assess the predictive uncertainty. An example of the predicted mean reflectivity and its uncertainty is shown in Fig. 3. Note that given our current study is focus on developing a risk-aware

trajectory planning framework, and due to page limitations, we do not present a detailed evaluation of the prediction performance here.

Figure 3: Radar reflectivity mean and uncertainty (standard deviation) prediction for 29 May 2016, 19:15 UTC.

2) *Air Traffic Configuration*: We consider three different traffic density scenarios, with 10, 20 and 30 aircraft crossing the area of interest during a one-hour period. In each independently sampled scenario, aircraft enter the region \mathcal{X} with entry times sampled uniformly distributed over a 30-minute window, and their priority is based on the time each aircraft enters. Origin and destination pairs for each flight are randomly determined within \mathcal{X} . During the flight, we limit the track angle change in all turning points to at most $3^\circ/\text{sec}$ [23]. Aircraft types are randomly sampled from the BADA v3.x database [11], and their speed is set to constant based on the recommended cruise speed for the selected aircraft type. For reference, we assume that each flight has a nominal trajectory planned without accounting for weather risk.

3) *Algorithm Parameters*: For each testing traffic scenario, we run the RAW-RRT* for 4000 iterations to ensure sufficient exploration of the solution space. The k-nearest search parameter here is chosen as $k = 15$ [24], and the discrete time step Δt for state transition in Eq. 5 is set to 60 seconds. The hazardous weather encounter threshold is set to $\xi = 5(\text{dBZ})$, with an allowable probability of violation set to $\epsilon = 0.05$. The non-dimensional weights of fuel burn ω_m and distance of flight ω_d , are set to $\frac{\omega_d}{\omega_m} = 1.2$.

Fig. 4 gives an example of the algorithm’s evolution over 4000 iterations. Green dots are the nodes that represent aircraft state vector added at each iteration, with darker colors corresponding to later iterations. Gray lines are the edges connecting each node to its parent. We can see that there are certain nodes identified as “risky” and subsequently rejected, leaving a blank region within the exploration space where the node expansion is restricted.

B. Analysis of Results

Fig. 5 presents an example of the trajectory evolution for a single aircraft and corresponding weather condition evolution at three different simulation times. In Fig. 5a, at simulation time $t = 1200$ seconds, the aircraft has not yet

Figure 4: An example of the RAW-RRT* evolution for a single trajectory in Polar Stereographic Projection. The final optimized trajectory that connects the start point to the goal point is shown as deep purple line.

reached the entry point. The weather avoidance trajectory planned by RAW-RRT* is represented by a dashed line, with each decision point marked as pink nodes. In Fig. 5b, at simulation time $t = 2400$ seconds, the aircraft enters the area of interest. The flown portion of the trajectory is represented by a solid line, while the remaining planned but to-to-be-flown path is showed as a dashed line. In Fig. 5c, at simulation time $t = 3600$ seconds, the aircraft has executed its planned trajectory. Instead of avoiding all weather regions, the trajectory traverses through a small weather-affected area, the overall risk remains zero throughout the flight.

Moreover, we can observe that the RAW-RRT* plans the trajectory by looking ahead at how the weather cells are expected to move. At $t = 1200$ seconds (Fig. 5a), the RAW-RRT* planned trajectory appears to pass through a region where the weather intensity estimation exceeds 20 dBZ. However, by the time the aircraft reaches that location between $t = 2400$ and $t = 3600$ seconds (Figs. 5b and 5c), the adverse weather cells have moved northward, leaving the flight path safer.

Fig. 6 shows the three traffic scenarios in the one-hour testing period, with 10, 20 and 30 aircraft. In all cases, the minimum separation requirement defined in Eq. (6) is satisfied. Fig. 7 shows the corresponding relative additional distances flown and fuel consumed across these scenarios, respectively, compared to the nominal trajectories without weather avoidance rerouting.

As seen in Fig. 7a, there is an increase in the average extra distances flown rate with an increase in the number of aircraft. This trend indicates that with higher traffic density, aircraft tend to follow longer paths to avoid potential conflicts. Consequently, we can see from Fig. 7b that these additional rerouting correspond to a rise in average fuel usage rate. Since each aircraft maintains a constant speed, the additional fuel consumption increases linearly with the extra distance flown.

Furthermore, the wider spread in results for extra distance with increasing traffic density suggests that more complex

(a) Simulation time $t = 1200$ (sec)

(b) Simulation time $t = 2400$ (sec)

(c) Simulation time $t = 3600$ (sec)

Figure 5: Example of the trajectory planned by RAW-RRT* and weather condition evolution over time in Polar Stereographic Projection. Before the flight enters the area of interest, the trajectory is planned iteratively as the new estimation of the weather state information is available. The overall weather risk of this flight $R_{\Gamma} = 1.7881 \times 10^{-7}$.

traffic conditions require enhanced conflict avoidance strategies. In these circumstances, the RAW-RRT* algorithm appears to adjust aircraft headings to maintain exposure to convective weather risks within an acceptable threshold while also avoiding conflicts with other aircraft, which consequently

(a) Scenario 1: aircraft = 10

(b) Scenario 2: aircraft = 20

(c) Scenario 3: aircraft = 30

Figure 6: RAW-RRT* trajectory planning results across three traffic scenarios in Polar Stereographic Projection. Due to the one-hour simulation period, some trajectories terminate before reaching their goal points.

leads to longer flight time as shown in Fig. 8.

From Fig. 8, we can observe that while some aircraft experience significant heading changes, others maintain a relatively steady course. These differences likely result from the varying weather conditions encountered by each aircraft, and from differences in their entry times that affect their conflict avoidance priority. On the other hand, these small

(a) Additional distance

(b) Additional fuel

Figure 7: Flight performance metrics for each flight across three traffic scenarios.

adjustments in heading suggest that the RAW-RRT* trajectory planning algorithm gives smooth flight paths.

Finally, Fig. 9 gives the logarithmic measure of each aircraft’s trajectory-wise risk across three testing traffic scenarios. As the airspace becomes more congested, the variability in risk values slightly increases. In other words, even though all flight paths remain within the acceptable risk threshold, there is a greater chance of exposing areas with higher weather risk when more aircraft share the same airspace.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present the RAW-RRT* algorithm for in-flight replanning of aircraft trajectories that are both conflict-free and risk-aware within en-route airspace affected by convective weather. The proposed framework replans the trajectories centrally at a constant flight level, and mimicking current operations, avoidance trajectories are not constrained to en-route procedures. Yet, future work could explore traffic in evolution (climbing or descending) and structured airspace scenarios, in which aircraft are required, for instance, to pass through predefined waypoints. The advantage of handling both conflict resolution and convective weather centrally is simplified modeling. This centralized approach also provides global solution to addressing complex multi-aircraft interac-

(a) Scenario 1: aircraft = 10

(b) Scenario 2: aircraft = 20

(c) Scenario 3: aircraft = 30

Figure 8: Heading change for each flight and the corresponding sampled aircraft type across three traffic scenarios. The change $\Delta\chi$ is based on the instantaneous heading change between consecutive time steps, i.e., $\Delta t = 60$ seconds.

tions efficiently. However, such approach neglects negotiation between aircraft crews and air traffic controllers, making it less realistic for practical operations. This leads to a potential future improvement that incorporates partially decentralized method, simulating negotiated trajectory solutions.

Moreover, the assumption of constant speed for the simplicity in the experiments could be relaxed in future work, as our proposed framework formulates speed as a variable in its

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is partially supported by the National Research Foundation, Singapore, and the Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore, under the Aviation Transformation Programme. Any opinions, findings and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not reflect the views of National Research Foundation, Singapore and the Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore.

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Figure 9: Trajectory-wise risk for each flight across three traffic scenarios. All flight remain within the $\epsilon = 0.05$ allowable risk threshold for encountering hazardous weather.

general form. It is also possible to consider varying speed and altitude for aircraft in the cases of turbulence avoidance, since aircraft crews might seek flight levels clear of turbulence [25].

We treat the probabilistic weather forecasting problem as an image-to-image translation problem using calibrated radar data to estimate future radar echo intensity and its uncertainty. We introduce the weather risk of a flight trajectory as the joint probability that the entire path falls in hazardous weather regions. By extending the traditional RRT* with capabilities of online risk assessment, we plan the trajectory with a 20-minute look-ahead horizon, handling both conflict avoidance and weather uncertainty in a probabilistic manner. The simulation results show that the RAW-RRT* algorithm gives smooth and efficient flight paths while maintaining the required safety separation and managing weather risk effectively. A natural extension of our multi-aircraft trajectory planning framework for adverse weather avoidance and conflict resolution would be to conduct a sensitivity analysis of the look-ahead horizon, quantifying the trajectory uncertainty associated with different lead times and analyzing the optimal horizon length required for effective conflict resolution.

Finally, we assess hazardous weather risk based solely on radar reflectivity. Possible improvements include incorporating storm structure and vertically integrated liquid to further quantify the operational impact. In addition, sensitivity analysis on the user-defined trajectory-wise weather risk threshold could provide insights into its effect on resulting trajectories and overall performance.

In future research, we also plan to incorporate additional weather characteristics, such as the shape of weather events, into the weather risk calculation. Weather patterns, such as round echoes from convective showers or steep gradient shapes indicating vertical shear, may provide further clues about potential hazards [26]. We also plan to account for the uncertainty in each aircraft's position. These improvements could lead to more robust conflict-free trajectory in complex weather environments.

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